

Disproof of Hodge Conjecture by Graph Theory

Jihyeon Yoon^[1]

December 13, 2023

Abstract

Hodge conjecture is turned out to be false in extension of graph theory based on its algebraic attribute.

1 Introduction

Hodge conjecture^[1] could be falsified by the graph relations with algebraic property derived from Fermat's Last Theorem^[3].

2 Hodge Conjecture

Hodge conjecture is as follows^[2]:

Let X be a non-singular complex projective manifold. Then every Hodge class on X is a linear combination with rational coefficients of the cohomology classes of complex subvarieties of X .

The property of Hodge class manifold is as follows with the given weight:

1. Abelian Operation of Manifold
2. One-to-One Relation of Manifold in Complex Conjugation
3. Availability in Cohomology of Manifold by Hodge Filtration

If any of upper given property could not be conserved in linear combination with rational coefficients of subvarieties, Hodge conjecture would be false.

3 Topological Property of Graph

Euler Characteristic Equation is as follows in manifold compact X , M , and N :

$$\begin{aligned}\chi(X) &= \sum (-1)^i h_i(X) \Rightarrow \chi(M \cup N) = \chi(M) + \chi(N) - \chi(M \cap N) \\ &\Rightarrow v - e + f = C \text{ s.t. } \dim(X) = 2\end{aligned}$$

For definition of function h_i , its unit count in elemental dimension of a compact. (For 0 dimension, it would be a count of dot in compact, 1 dimension would be a count of line, 2 dimension would be a count of surface, and so on.)

For graph being at least 2-dimensional manifold, Euler Characteristic Equation would follow as X .

4 Implication of Fermat's Last Theorem in Topology

From previous discussion of Fermat's Last Theorem[3], Any relation of algebraic expansion in matrix follows:

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{s.t. Matrix } M \text{ in } (1 \times p), N \text{ as } (1 \times q), L \text{ as } (1 \times r), \sum MM^T = p, \sum NN^T = q, \sum LL^T = r \\ & \Rightarrow (MM^T)^n + (NN^T)^n = (LL^T)^n \Rightarrow ((1 \times p) \cdot (p \times 1))^n + ((1 \times q) \cdot (q \times 1))^n = ((1 \times r) \cdot (r \times 1))^n \\ & \Rightarrow n = 1 \text{ or } 2 \end{aligned}$$

And so[4]:

$$\forall a, \forall b \in \mathbb{Q}, a \geq 1, b \geq 1 \Rightarrow 2 \leq a + b \leq a^2 + b^2 \leq 2^{a+b}$$

And now, assuming a graph G_M , G_N , and G_L with its vertices as V_M , V_N , and V_L , having its relation in vertices' length in each matrix M , N , and L . If then, sum total of any graph structure given in combination with length size of p and q couldn't be larger than $\sqrt{2^{p+q}}$. This is a main reason for falsification of the Hodge conjecture, as it could not restrict range itself in countable amount set. If the combination of vertices couldn't be restricted in rational range, some Hodge classes couldn't be represented in rational coefficients. More specifically, while dimensional conversion to any graph manifold during projection, isomorphism to graph could not be kept with one-to-one relation in the manifold to infinite dimensions.

5 Conclusion

1. Non-singular complex manifold could be projected into complex space as graph.
2. By interpreting projection into connected graph, projection of subvarieties of the manifold could not be restricted to rational range while conserving its Hodge class property.
3. Hodge conjecture is turned out to be false.

References

- [1] Pierre Deligne. "The Hodge conjecture". In: *The millennium prize problems* (2000), pp. 45–53.
- [2] Wikipedia. *Hodge conjecture* — Wikipedia, The Free Encyclopedia. <http://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Hodge%20conjecture&oldid=1188123322>. [Online; accessed 12-December-2023]. 2023.
- [3] Jihyeon Yoon. *Understanding Fermat's Last Theorem through Matrix-Graph Relation*. June 2023. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.8001801](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8001801). URL: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8001801>.
- [4] Jihyeon Yoon. *Understanding Riemann Hypothesis by Matrix-Graph Relation*. June 2023. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.8001808](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8001808). URL: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8001808>.

Notes

1. Jihyeon Yoon is a freelancer programmer.
Yeongdeungpo-gu, Seoul, 07429,
Seoul, South Korea
E-mail: somehowme@gmail.com, flyingtext@nate.com
ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9610-0994>